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**Polynuclear Photographic Sensitising Dyes
Derived from 4,4'-p-Phenylene
Bis-(2-Methyl Thiazole), Part-II.**

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IN the present investigation a number of symmetrical non-ionic tetranuclear dyes (I) with two central quaternary thiazole residues, two ketomethylene residues and two (=CH-CH=)_n chains derived from the diquaternary salt of 4,4'-p-phenylene bis-(2-methyl thiazole) have been prepared. The variable acidic

nuclei were derived from various ketomethylene compounds like 2-phenyl oxazolone, 2-benzylthio-thiazolone, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone, N,N-diphenyl-thio-barbituric acid and N-phenyl rhodanine.

(I) (A = Variable Acidic nuclei n=1, 2)

The absorption maxima of these dyes were measured. The vinylenic shift for these tetranuclear dyes has been found to be between 75 nm to 92 nm by comparing the absorption maxima data of the tetranuclear dyes (I, n=1) with their higher vinylenic homologues (I, n=2). The vinylenic shifts vary with the nature of the variable nuclei used for the preparation of these dyes.

Experimental

4,4'-p-Phenylene-bis-(2-methyl thiazole) methiodide has been prepared from 1,4-diacetyl benzene¹.

Symmetrical non-ionic tetranuclear dyes (Compound No. 1)

4-Ethoxymethylene-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone² (0.46g) and 4,4'-p-phenylene-bis-(2-methyl thiazole) methiodide (0.8g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine (2-drops) for 10 minutes. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The desired product separated on cooling was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. m.p.-192° (decomp); yield. 30% (Found C, 67.85; H, 4.58; N, 12.51; S, 9.49%. C₃₈H₃₈N₆O₂S₂ requires C, 68.26; H, 4.64; N, 12.57; S, 9.58%).

TABLE 1—TETRANUCLEAR DYES DERIVED FROM 4,4'-p-PHENYLENE-BIS-(2-METHYLTHIAZOLE)

(Structure—I)

Sl. No.	Nature of acidic nucleus 'A'	Value of 'n'	M. P. °C	Yield %	Abs. Max in nm.	Sulphur %		Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	1-methyl-3-phenyl pyrazolone	1	192 (d)	30	483	9.49	9.58	12.51	12.57
2.	-do-	2	206 (d)	25	575	8.78	8.89	11.53	11.67
3.	N-phenyl rhodanine	1	220	25	515	25.03	26.01	7.17	7.58
4.	-do-	2	206 (d)	15	606	24.50	24.61	6.84	7.18
5.	N, N-diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	1	>206	20	475	13.05	14.04	8.81	9.21
6.	-d-	2	247 (d)	25	560	13.17	13.27	8.39	8.71
7.	2-benzyl thiothiazolone	1	173 (d)	15	496	24.05	25.07	6.89	7.31
8.	2-phenyl oxazolone	1	>250	15	523	9.83	9.97	8.43	8.72

Other dyes were prepared by condensing the methiodide with ethoxymethylene or acetanilido methylene derivatives of other ketomethylene compounds².

The higher vinylene homologue of the above dye (Table 1 Compound No. 2) was obtained by the condensation of the desired methiodide (0.4g) with 4-(3-acetanilido-allylidene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone² (0.35g) in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine. The compound was isolated in usual manner. m.p.-206° (decomp); yield-25% (Found C, 69.48; H, 4.87; N, 11.53; S, 8.78%. C₄₂H₃₆N₆O₂S₂ requires C, 70.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.67; S, 8.89%). Other dyes of this type were prepared in similar manner using either acetanilido allylidene or methoxy allylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds².

The analytical data, m.p.s etc. of all these dyes are described in Table 1.

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Coordination Compounds of Copper(II) Derived from Schiff's bases

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THE use of aromatic Schiff's bases derived from various aldehydes and amines as either anionic monofunctional mono or multidentate or neutral mono or multidentate ligands has attracted the attention

of workers in previous years¹⁻⁴. In the present paper the interaction of aniline and toluidines with benzaldehyde in alcohol has been studied and these Schiff's bases on treatment with copper(II) salts are found to give bright green molecular compounds of 1:1 stoichiometry, whose structures have been determined on the basis of analytical and spectroscopic data.

Discussion

The electronic spectra of complexes contain three sharp bands near 235 nm, 320 nm and 680 nm. The first two of these are also seen in the spectra of free Schiff's bases and the former one corresponds to the perturbed benzene ring transition of the amine fragment and the latter to the whole aromatic molecule oriented *trans* with respect to the double bond^{5,6}. The last one is the characteristic d-d transition of copper(II) in planar environment.

In the i.r. spectra of complexes one broad band appears around 3400 cm⁻¹ which is absent in the spectra of free Schiff's bases. It thus shows that all complexes contain coordinated water^{7,8}. The band at 1600±10 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the azomethine stretch, which in free ligands is observed at 1620±10 cm⁻¹. This small negative shift although an indication of coordination also shows the reduced ability of the Schiff's bases to act as ligands for copper(II), due to steric reasons as already reported⁹⁻¹¹. The phthalate complexes show the asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ stretches at 1690±10 and 1417±40 cm⁻¹ characteristic of co-ordinated carboxylate ion¹². The molar conductances of these complexes in nitrobenzene are also almost zero, as expected in view of their non electrolytic nature. The sulphate complex on the other hand behaves as 1:1 electrolyte and the ν₃ and ν₄ transitions of uncoordinated sulphate ion are seen at 1120 and 650 cm⁻¹ in the i.r. spectra.

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TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE (IN NITROBENZENE) AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Formula	% Cu	% C	% H	% N	Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ in mhos	μ _{eff} in B. M
1. [Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)]SO ₄	16.51 (16.10)	39.72 (39.56)	4.52 (4.62)	3.62 (3.55)	20.16	1.886
2. [Cu(H ₂ O)(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	15.01 (14.89)	59.43 (59.03)	3.88 (3.98)	3.22 (3.28)	0.18	1.888
3. [Cu(H ₂ O)(o-C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.50 (14.41)	59.50 (59.90)	4.28 (4.86)	3.21 (3.18)	0.13	1.888
4. [Cu(H ₂ O)(m-C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.62	59.82	4.72	3.35	0.08	1.884
5. [Cu(H ₂ O)(p-C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.75	60.02	4.50	3.50	0.07	1.882